

Types of Twins

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Abstract

There are two type of twin, monozygotic (identical), and dizygotic (fraternal) twins. Twins, refers to embryos for the same pregnancy that arise from either one fertilized oocyte (monozygotic twin) or from different oocytes fertilized by different sperms (dizygotic twin). Pregnant with twins is not rare, the rate of the twins in live births is 1 in 80, ie, in 40 babies there is 1 is twin. The rate of the dizygotic twins different from rate of the monozygotic twins. Membranes of the placenta are formed in the early stages of the embryonic development. Distinguish the type of the twins may depend on their placental membranes. Abnormalities (congenital anomalies) associated with twins higher than with the singleton fetus.

Keywords: *Twins, monozygotic, dizygotic, fertilization, placenta, amniotic membrane, chorionic membrane, Congenital anomalies.*

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Introduction

Twins, refers to embryos for the same pregnancy that arise from either one fertilized oocyte or from different oocytes fertilized by different sperms, monozygotic and dizygotic, respectively. All monozygotic would be the same sex, both are a boy or both are a girl, while the dizygotic half of them are same sex, and the other half are deferent sex (Weinberg, 1902).

Term Identical refers to monozygotic twins, this is because their genetic makeup would be identical, this depends on the monozygotic come from the same zygote (one oocyte fertilized by one sperm). Thus, the environmental factors are main reason to differences between twins of this type. While in the other type of dizygotic twine known as fraternal twins (two oocytes fertilized by two sperm), the environmental and genetic factors contribute to differences between twins (Phelan, 1993; Galton, 1875).

Pregnant with twins is not rare, the rate of twins in live births is 1 in 80, ie, in 40 babies there is 1 is twin (Nylander, 1975). The rate of the dizygotic twins different from rate of the monozygotic twins, so there is a large discrepancy between the two rates (Kiely & Kiely, 2001; Murphy & Hey, 1997). In the USA and Europe there about 10-20 from 1000 live births are twins, in African- Americans about 26 in 1000 newborn babies are a twin, in Africa approximately 40 in 1000, also in Asia about 6 in 1000 live births (Hall, 2003), 1 to 2 % in Australia (Laws & Sullivan, 2004). Per 1000 newborn there are less than 9 twin births, in India (Smits & Monden, 2011). Increased rate conceptions with twins' livebirths (dizygotic twins) due to increase use of the infertility drugs and *in-vitro fertilization* (IVF) since from 1980 (Machin et al., 1999; Tong, 2000). The rate of pregnant with more than one embryo assisted pregnant (Assisted Reproductive Techniques (ART)) is 2.25 times

more than normal pregnant (Vitthala et al., 2009).

Also should be noted, that abnormalities (congenital anomalies) associated with twins higher than with the singleton fetus (Dodd et al., 2011). The mortality rate in the twins higher than in the singleton conception, because preterm birth, twin to twin transfusion, intrauterine growth restriction, death of the one of the twins, and increased incidence of medical complications in the twin more than in the singleton pregnant (Dodd et al., 2003). Congenital anomalies such as neural tube defects, trisomies and gastrointestinal tract structural anomalies (Doyle, 1996), dislocation hips, clubfeet, and greater moulding of the head (Hall, 1996; Machin et al., 1999), occur in twins more than singleton conception (Doyle, 1996).

Placenta and Membranes in Twins

Membranes of the placenta are formed in the early stages of the embryonic development. Distinguish the type of the twins may depend on their placental membranes. indeed, twins are currently being classified according to their membranes (Benirschke, 1961; Benirschke & Kim, 1973a; 1973b).

Dizygotic Twin

This type of twin result from shedding of two ovum in same time and fertilization by two sperm forming two zygotes (fertilized oocyte) (Sadler, 2019). Every month, during ovarian cycle mature more than 15 follicle in same ovary that may cause ovulation more than one ovum leading to pregnant with dizygotic twins (Keith et al., 1995; Nylander, 1981). each of them individually implantation in the endometrium of the uterus, and form own amniotic membrane, chorionic membrane, and own placenta figure (1), sometimes may fuse the placentas because are so close together, also may fuse its chorionic membrane (Sadler, 2019). Certainly, each embryo of fraternal twins it's have own placenta and membrane (Dizygotic twins have separate placentas and membranes) (Hall, 2003). According to that, the genetic constitutions is different. So, the sex of twins may or may not different, different blood groups and different of external appearance (Sadler, 2019). One of the

most important factors associated with spontaneous dizygotic twin is increase concentration of the follicular stimulating hormone (FSH), there are more than cause lead to increase FSH such as old, heavy, and tall mother, and season, geography, and ethnic origin (Nylander, 1981; Nylander, 1975). When studying all pregnancy cases with dizygotic twin noted increased in concentration of the FSH, this increase is associated with using the fertility drugs (Kiely & Kiely, 2001; Tong, 2000). Also noted the increased in pregnancy with dizygotic twin in the summer months. In other hand, decrease in spontaneous dizygotic twin with starvation and urbanization (Nylander, 1981).

Figure 1. Dizygotic Twins; Each of Them Have Own Placenta, Chorionic, and Amniotic

Monozygotic Twin

As mentioned earlier, this type of twins arise from single oocyte fertilized by single sperm and form zygote. Then, separated its cells at different stage of development, the separation might be in blastomeres (two cells) or even after formation of the primitive streak. So, there are different forming of placenta and its membranes for these twins. 70-75 % of this type of twins intrauterine live with common placenta and separate amnion and chorionic membranes, while 25-30 of these twins have separate placenta, amnion, and chorionic membranes. In rare cases, 1-2% the twins intrauterine live with common placenta and membranes (Hall, 2003) figure (2). In

human, the causes of the conception with monozygotic twins are unknown (Richards et al., 1990). This type of twin represent approximately third of the spontaneous twins (Murphy & Hey, 1997). Increase conception with monozygotic twin 2-5 times by *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) because the breaks in the zona pellocida for any reason. Monozygotic twins by IVF are usually were dichorionic and diamniotic, that mean the separation was in early stage (Edwards et al., 1986). From these, understand there are many causes to pregnant with monozygotic twins in human such as IVF, break in zona pellocida, damage to the inner cells mass, drugs (for fertilization or ovulation) and others (Hall, 2001; Vitthala et al., 2009).

Can be divided of this type of twine according to type of placenta (Machin et al., 1999). It is possible to estimate time of twins events through their placenta and its membranes. When the each embryo have its own placenta, amnion, and chorionic, this type usually occurs before third day of development, but if the placenta is common for two embryos and separate amnion and chorionic, this type of monozygotic twins occurs between fourth and sixth day of development. Last, if the both embryos common placenta common membranes, in this case the separation occurs after form primitive streak, this case is rare (Hall, 2003).

Figure 2. Monozygotic Twins; Types of Placenta, Chorionic, and Amnion

The conjoined twin are incomplete twin (incomplete separation), it's usually monozygotic twin figure (3), for every 400

monozygotic twin births there is 1 is conjoined twin (Phelan, 1993; Machin, 1993). This case usually event after 2 week of embryonic development, ie, after formation of primitive streak (Boklage, 1987). Approximately 40 to 60 % of the conjoined twin, in the past, they are stillborn, now the rate has decreased due to the health care, early diagnosis, and advances in surgical. Major of the conjoined twin (50%) have structural anomalies.

Figure 3. Types of the Conjoined Twins

Congenital anomalies divided into malformations, deformations, and disruptions (Opitz et al., 1987), all these types might be frequency in monozygotic twins. These abnormalities such as disruptions may be lead to death one twins. Approximately 10% of monozygotic twins are born (liveborn and miscarriages) with a congenital anomalies (Myriantopoulos, 1975).

Conclusion

1. Two type of twin, monozygotic twin, that arise from one fertilized oocyte, and dizygotic twin, that arise from different oocytes fertilized by different sperms.
2. Pregnant with twins is not rare. The rate of the dizygotic twins different from rate of the monozygotic twins.
3. Distinguish the type of the twins may depend on their placental membranes.
4. Abnormalities associated with twins higher than with the singleton fetus.

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